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Machine Learning-based classification of Sentinel-1 backscattering coefficients using Generated Plant Schematics

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Abstract

We propose a data-driven method using a convolutional neural network (CNN) to classify plant growth stages, using Sentinel-1 SAR backscattering values and computer-generated schematics representing plant development. Opposed to the physics-based approaches of BS simulation such as integral equation modelling, this approach is data-driven and has the potential to be more robust. A total of five field measurement campaigns were run over the five months and we collected the soil roughness and wheat canopy parameters. Data was used to randomly generate the synthetic images which were further used to train and test a CNN. Computer-generated plant schematics are digital representations of the soil and plant layer which are the two main components that affect the BS coefficients. Results show that the model successfully classified five stages of the wheat canopy growth with the highest test accuracy of 96.4%.

1 Introduction

SAR is a technique to generate high-resolution images of the ground or other targets using radar signals. Movement of the SAR platform (airborne, spacecraft, etc.) makes it possible to synthetically increase the aperture of the radar, a larger aperture results in higher resolution. Sentinel-1 is an imaging radar mission launched by the European Space Agency under the Copernicus program and it provides continuous all-weather, day-and-night imagery at C-band (5.405 GHz). The BS coefficients obtained from Sentinel-1 SAR data are important for agriculture because they reveal information about the soil and plants. This potentially improves the monitoring quality and efficiency. SAR remote sensing is sensitive to the dielectric and geometrical characteristics of the soil and plants. Higher moisture level in these

objects causes an increase in the dielectric constant [1]. In this paper, we only considered the geometrical shapes of the plants.

Simulation of SAR BS coefficients has been an interest of research in the last few decades. It has many applications in radar remote sensing such as sensor and algorithm design, mission planning, geo-referencing, SAR data analysis and interpretation, etc. However, one model is not suitable for all scenarios or applications, thus, many simulation models have been developed [2]. There are three main categories of SAR simulation models, empirical, semi-empirical and physics-based [3]. An empirical model, Dubois [4], and semi-empirical models such as Oh models [5–8] rely on detailed ground-truth data for calibration. The most popular physics-based models are the Integral Equation Model (IEM) [9] and derived versions of it such as IEM_B by Baghdadi [10–15], the Advanced Integral Equation Model (AIEM) [16] and the "Tor Vergata" model [17].

Recent advancements in computer power made complex machine learning (ML) models applicable and in our approach, we employed a deep convolutional neural network (CNN) to estimate Sentinel-1 BS coefficients and classify plant development stages. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: methodology and data are described in Section 2, Section 3 presents the experimental results, and the final section concludes the paper.

2 Methodology and Data

The data was generated based on plant statistics that were measured during in situ measurement campaigns. A total of five in situ measurements were performed on a wheat crop belonging to the National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet Brasov, Romania located at the following GPS location: 45°40'22.2"N, 25°32'28.1"E. Figure 2 (a) presents a broad view of the study area captured by Sentinel-2, resolution of 500×500 pixels while Figure 2 (b) is 150×150 pixel zoomed-in depiction of a specific field within this area, distinguished by a cyan-colored polygon, which outlines the region where detailed measurements and observations were conducted. The plant characteristics and the dates of the five measurement campaigns performed in 2023 are detailed in Table 1. Only the plant stage-3 measurement campaign was performed one day after the satellite pass. For all the others Sentinel-1 passed over the area of interest in the same day. The average plant height increases until the ripening (stages 1 to 3).

The bare soil case is the first field measurement where we used a pinboard [18] to measure the soil roughness (SR). SR is a broad term often referred to as soil microrelief that can be divided into individual indices that describe different characteristics of the soil. One of them and the one used in this study is random roughness that is related to soil aggregate stability [19]. The term was introduced by Burwell et al. (1963) [20] to describe the elevation

Figure 1: Block diagram of the workflow.

Figure 2: Figure (a) shows a 500×500 pixel overview of the area from Sentinel-2; Figure (b) is a detailed 150×150 pixel zoom highlighting the specific field marked by a cyan polygon where measurements were conducted.

variations at random points on the soil surface. Cremers et al. (1996) suggested that the standard deviation of height measurements, once slope effects are removed, is adequate for such measurements [21]. This approach was adopted as our definition of soil roughness. A total of 10 measurements were performed and 20 plant samples were analyzed in each plant stage. Figure 3 shows the application of pinboard on the soil surface and images of the plants from different development stages. It also shows a schematic sample image per stage on the right-hand side, starting from bare soil and the last one being the final stage of wheat canopy where crops are ready to be harvested.

Wheat stem, head and leaves were created randomly but the randomness of their sizes was controlled by the minimum and maximum boundaries which were obtained from real wheat canopies. Soil surface and plants are

Table 1: The dates (all in 2023) and plant characteristics [cm] for the five in situ measurement campaigns.

	S0	S1	S2	S3	S4
Date	24/03	25/05	09/06	30/06	27/07
Min height	-	12.5	38.8	55.2	47.6
Max height	-	26	63.9	80.2	84.3
Avg height	-	19.8	52.3	69.2	64.4
Min # leaves	-	4	4	3	3
Max # leaves	-	7	7	4	4
Avg # leaves	-	5	5	4	4
Min leaf length	-	13.5	5	7	6.2
Max leaf length	-	26.1	25.1	26.1	31
Avg leaf length	-	19.2	16.8	18.1	16.8

calibrated to represent real objects and plants were placed with a 12.5 *cm* distance between each other. This placement is a perpendicular side view to the sowing direction. Moreover, we added the curvature feature to the leaves to resemble the real wheat canopy by using the Bezier curve function.

For the ML model, we chose a convolutional neural network, in particular - ResNet-18 model [22]. Deep residual networks, like ResNet-18, utilize residual blocks with skip connections to allow the flow of data through the network. This addresses the vanishing gradient problem and makes training of very deep neural networks effective. This architecture significantly improves learning efficiency and performance by letting layers learn updates to the identity function, rather than learning the target mapping from scratch. Per stage including bare soil case, 1000 images were generated, a total of 5000 images. From these images, 80% of them were used for training and 20% for testing the model. However, we modified the input layer to receive one-channel binary images instead of three channels as default, output is also modified to classify images into five classes as opposed to the original 1000 classes. The model was trained and tested for 20 epochs with a learning rate of 0.0001 without any learning rate decay. We employed Cross-Entropy Loss for the classification task due to its effectiveness in multi-class scenarios, alongside the Adam optimizer for its adaptive learning rate features. We used average values of BS coefficients over the entire field from five campaigns as labels, each grouped to the 1000 images and these labels (target values) can be interpreted differently. The main interpretation is the classification of plant growth stages, which is obtained by associating Sentinel-1 BS coefficients with different plant growth stages that are identified through CNN. This approach is different from direct estimation of BS, as it uses classifications of generated plant schematics to infer BS values. Table 2 shows

(a) Pinboard on bare soil

(b) Bare soil schematic

(c) Plant growth stage-1

(d) Plant schematic growth stage-1

(e) Plant growth stage-2

(f) Plant schematic growth stage-2

(g) Plant growth stage-3

(h) Plant schematic growth stage-3

(i) Plant growth stage-4

(j) Plant schematic growth stage-4

Figure 3: Bare soil and plant growth stages.

the minimum, maximum and average of Sentinel-1 BS values for each stage.

Table 2: Bare soil, four different wheat plant stages, and corresponding minimum and maximum BS coefficients.

Stage	Min BS (dB)	Max BS (dB)	Avg BS (dB)
Bare soil	-15.21	-11.79	-13.13
Plant stage-1	-14.73	-11.14	-13.49
Plant stage-2	-18.66	-13.09	-17.24
Plant stage-3	-13.46	-10.72	-11.91
Plant stage-4	-8.36	-5.87	-7.42

Figure 4 shows the k-density distribution of BS coefficients. The distribution of BS coefficients of plant growth stage-2 is placed on the very left side of the bare soil distribution suggesting a weaker radar signature. While the final stage of the plant growth has the highest coefficients suggesting a stronger radar signature. To obtain BS values SAR data needs to be processed and we used SNAP software to accomplish it while image generation and model training were implemented in Python. Sentinel-1 SAR data processing involves the following steps: calibration, speckle filtering, Range-Doppler terrain correction, and conversion of the band from linear to logarithmic (dB). Figure 1 illustrates the workflow from data collection to classification.

3 Results

Results obtained from the training and testing are shown in Figure 5. The graph shows the accuracy of the model over 20 epochs. One can observe that accuracy on the test set fluctuated but these fluctuations have been minor after the 10th epoch. Additionally, we also trained the model with a higher number of epochs with even deeper networks, however, we did not observe much difference in the results. Desirable results were possible to achieve with a smaller number of epochs and a less complex network. Overall, 100% accuracy on the training set and 96.4% on the test set were obtained. Based on the results we can say that the model successfully learned to differentiate between bare soil and different plant growth stages.

Figure 4: K-density estimation of BS coefficients.

Figure 5: Model accuracy on train and test data.

4 Conclusions

In this paper, we present the generation process of randomly generated plant schematics based on in situ measurements of a real wheat crop in the Brasov area, Romania. The resulting dataset was used to train a ResNet-18 model, in order to learn the correspondence between the scene geometry as represented by the computer-generated plant schematics and the BS coefficients of the radar signal from the Sentinel-1 data. The dataset consists of 5000 computer-generated grayscale images representing plant schematics, 1000

per plant stage. The experiment shows good potential in using CNN models for predicting the growth stages of plants and their signature on Sentinel-1 SAR. In the future by expanding the data and generating more detailed visual schematics, CNN models have the potential to predict a wider range of parameters.

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References

- [1] Chang an LIU, Zhong xin CHEN, Yun SHAO, Jin song CHEN, Tuya Hasi, and Hai zhu PAN, “Research advances of sar remote sensing for agriculture applications: A review,” *Journal of Integrative Agriculture*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 506–525, 2019.
- [2] Timo Balz, Horst Hammer, and Stefan Auer, “Potentials and limitations of sar image simulators – a comparative study of three simulation approaches,” *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, vol. 101, pp. 102–109, 2015.
- [3] Mohammad Choker, Nicolas Baghdadi, Mehrez Zribi, Mohammad El Hajj, Simonetta Paloscia, Niko E. C. Verhoest, Hans Lievens, and Francesco Mattia, “Evaluation of the oh, dubois and iem backscatter models using a large dataset of sar data and experimental soil measurements,” *Water*, vol. 9, no. 1, 2017.
- [4] P.C. Dubois, J. van Zyl, and T. Engman, “Measuring soil moisture with imaging radars,” *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 915–926, 1995.

- [5] Yisok Oh, “Quantitative retrieval of soil moisture content and surface roughness from multipolarized radar observations of bare soil surfaces,” *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 596–601, 2004.
- [6] Y. Oh, K. Sarabandi, and F.T. Ulaby, “An empirical model and an inversion technique for radar scattering from bare soil surfaces,” *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 370–381, 1992.
- [7] Yisok Oh, Kamal Sarabandi, and Fawwaz T Ulaby, “An inversion algorithm for retrieving soil moisture and surface roughness from polarimetric radar observation,” in *Proceedings of IGARSS’94-1994 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*. IEEE, 1994, vol. 3, pp. 1582–1584.
- [8] Y. Oh, K. Sarabandi, and F.T. Ulaby, “Semi-empirical model of the ensemble-averaged differential mueller matrix for microwave backscattering from bare soil surfaces,” *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 40, no. 6, pp. 1348–1355, 2002.
- [9] A.K. Fung, Z. Li, and K.S. Chen, “Backscattering from a randomly rough dielectric surface,” *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 356–369, 1992.
- [10] A. Chanzy N. Baghdadi, C. King and J. P. Wigneron, “An empirical calibration of the integral equation model based on sar data, soil moisture and surface roughness measurement over bare soils,” *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 23, no. 20, pp. 4325–4340, 2002.
- [11] M. Zribi M. Sahebi C. King N. Baghdadi, I. Gherboudj and F. Bonn, “Semi-empirical calibration of the iem backscattering model using radar images and moisture and roughness field measurements,” *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 25, no. 18, pp. 3593–3623, 2004.
- [12] N. Holah N. Baghdadi and M. Zribi, “Calibration of the integral equation model for sar data in c-band and hh and vv polarizations,” *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 805–816, 2006.
- [13] Nicolas Baghdadi, Jad Abou Chaaya, and Mehrez Zribi, “Semiempirical calibration of the integral equation model for sar data in c-band and cross polarization using radar images and field measurements,” *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 14–18, 2011.
- [14] Nicolas Baghdadi, Elie Saba, Maelle Aubert, Mehrez Zribi, and Frederic Baup, “Evaluation of radar backscattering models iem, oh, and dubois for sar data in x-band over bare soils,” *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 1160–1164, 2011.

- [15] Nicolas Baghdadi, Mehrez Zribi, Simonetta Paloscia, Niko E. C. Verhoest, Hans Lievens, Frederic Baup, and Francesco Mattia, “Semi-empirical calibration of the integral equation model for co-polarized l-band backscattering,” *Remote Sensing*, vol. 7, no. 10, pp. 13626–13640, 2015.
- [16] K.S. Chen, Tzong-Dar Wu, Leung Tsang, Qin Li, Jiancheng Shi, and A.K. Fung, “Emission of rough surfaces calculated by the integral equation method with comparison to three-dimensional moment method simulations,” *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 90–101, 2003.
- [17] P Ferrazzoli, “Numerical model of microwave backscattering and emission from terrain covered with vegetation,” *The Applied Computational Electromagnetics Society Journal (ACES)*, pp. 175–191, 1991.
- [18] RR Allmaras, Robert E Burwell, William E Larson, Robert F Holt, et al., “Total porosity and random roughness of the interrow zone as influenced by tillage,” 1966.
- [19] Ingrid Takken, “Effects of soil roughness on overland flow and erosion,” 2000.
- [20] RE Burwell, RR Allmaras, and MJSSSoAJ Amemiya, “A field measurement of total porosity and surface microrelief of soils,” *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 697–700, 1963.
- [21] NHDT Cremers, PM Van Dijk, APJ De Roo, and MA Verzandvoort, “Spatial and temporal variability of soil surface roughness and the application in hydrological and soil erosion modelling,” *Hydrological processes*, vol. 10, no. 8, pp. 1035–1047, 1996.
- [22] Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, and Jian Sun, “Deep residual learning for image recognition,” 2015.